

PARABOLALAR OILASI BO'YICHA BERILGAN INTEGRALGA ASOSLANIB INTEGRAL OSTIDAGI NOMA'LUM FUNKSIYANI TIKLASH MASALASI YECHIMINING YAGONALIGI HAQIDAGI TEOREMA

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Volter tipidagi integral geometriyaning masalalari yangi sinfga tadqiq etiladi. Ma'lumki, integral geometriya masalalari turg'unlik xarakteri bo'yicha kuchsiz nokorrekt va kuchli nokorrekt masalalariga bo'linadi. Yagonalik teoremasi isbotlandi, teskarilanish formulasi keltirib chiqarildi va chekli silliqli sohasida turg'unlik bahosi olindi, bu shundan dalolat beradiki qo'yilgan masala kuchsiz nokorrekt.

Kalit so'zlar: parabolalar oilasi, Furiye alashtirishi, yagonalik teoremasi, kuchli nokorrekt masalalari, teskarilanish teoremasi.

Аннотация. В статье исследуются задачи интегральной геометрии типа Вольтера до нового класса. Известно, что задачи интегральной геометрии по характеру застоя делятся на слабо некорректные и сильно некорректные. Доказана теорема единственности, выведена формула обращения и получена оценка устойчивости в конечном гладком поле, что указывает на слабо некорректность данной задачи.

Ключевые слова: семейство парабол, преобразование Фурье, теорема единственности, сильные некорректные задачи, теорема обращения.

Annotation. In this article, problems of Voltaire-type integral geometry are investigated to a new class. It is known that problems of integral geometry are divided into weakly incorrect and strongly incorrect problems according to the character of stagnation. The uniqueness theorem was proved, the inversion formula was derived, and the stability estimate in the finite smooth field was obtained, which indicates that the given problem is weakly ill-posed.

Key words: family of parabolas, Fourier transform, uniqueness theorem, strong ill-posed problems, inversion theorem.

Biz foydalanadigan belgilashlarni kiritamiz:

$$(x, y) \in R^2, \quad (\xi, \eta) \in R^2, \quad \lambda \in R^1, \quad \mu \in R^1$$

Masalaning qo'yilishi.

$\{P(x, y)\}$ - R_+^2 dagi parabolalar oilasi bo'lsin. Oilaning ixtiyoriy $P(x, y)$ egri chiziqlari

$$P(x, y) = \{(\xi, \eta) : (y - \eta) = (x - \xi)^2, 0 \leq \eta\}.$$

munosabatlar bilan aniqlanadi.

1.Masala. Agar barcha $(x, y) \in R_+^2$ lar uchun $u(\bullet)$ funksiyadan $P(x, y)$ chiziqlar bo'yicha

$$\int_{x-\sqrt{y}}^{x+\sqrt{y}} g(x, \xi) u(\xi, \psi(x, y, \xi)) d\xi = f(x, y) \quad (1)$$

integrallar ma'lum bo'lsa, ikki o'zgaruvchili $u(x, y)$ funksiyani toping, bu yerda

$$g(x, \xi) = 2 |x - \xi| = 2(x - \xi) \operatorname{sgn}(x - \xi) \quad (2)$$

$u(x, y)$ funksiyalar ikkinchi tartibgacha uzluksiz xususiy hosilalarga ega bo'lgan R_+^2 da tashuvchisi bilan finit bo'lgan U sinfdagi funksiyalar:

$$\operatorname{Supp} u \subset D = \{(x, y) : -a < x < a, 0 < a < \infty, 0 < y < l, l < \infty\}$$

Quyidagi funksiyalarni kiritamiz

$$I(\lambda, \mu) = \int_0^{\infty} e^{i\mu\tau} \cos \lambda\sqrt{\tau} d\tau \quad (3)$$

$$I_1(\lambda, \mu) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-i\mu y} \frac{d\mu}{(1 + \mu^4)I(\lambda, \mu)} \quad (4)$$

$$I_2(x - \xi, y - \eta) = -\frac{1}{2} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-i\lambda x} \frac{I_1(\lambda, y)}{1 + \lambda^4} d\lambda \quad (5)$$

Quyidagi teorema o'rinli.

1. Teorema. $f(x, y)$ funksiyalar barcha $y \geq 0$ lar uchun ma'lum bo'lsin. U holda 1-masalaning yechimi yechimi U finit funksiyalar sinfidagi yagona

$$u(x, y) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} I_2(x - \xi, y - \eta) \left(E + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \xi^2}\right) \left(E + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \eta^2}\right) f(\xi, \eta) d\xi d\eta \quad (6)$$

ifodalash o'rinli va quyidagi tengsizlik bajariladi $\|u\|_{L_2} \leq C \|f\|_{W_2^2(R_+^2)}$ Bu yerda C - o'zgarmas son.

Isbot. (1) tenglamani quyidagicha almashtirish yordamida qulay ko'rinishga keltiramiz:

$$\eta - y = -(\xi - x)^2,$$

$$\eta = y - (\xi - x)^2 \Rightarrow (\xi - x)^2 = y - \eta$$

$$\xi - x = -\sqrt{y - \eta}, \quad \xi = x - \sqrt{y - \eta} \Rightarrow d\xi = \frac{d\eta}{2\sqrt{y - \eta}}$$

$$\xi - x = \sqrt{y - \eta}, \quad \xi = x + \sqrt{y - \eta} \Rightarrow d\xi = -\frac{d\eta}{2\sqrt{y - \eta}}$$

$$\psi(x, y, \xi) : 1) \psi(x, y, \xi) = y \quad 2) \psi(x, y, \xi) < y, \quad \xi \neq x$$

$$3) \psi(x, y, x + \xi) = \psi(x, y, x - \xi) ; \quad \psi(x, y, x \pm \sqrt{y}) = 0$$

(1) tenglamadan $d\eta$ bo'yicha integralga o'tib va (2) ni (1) ga qo'yib quyidagi integralni hosil qilamiz:

$$\int_{x-\sqrt{y}}^{x+\sqrt{y}} 2|x-\xi| u(\xi, \psi(x, y, \xi)) d\xi = \int_{x-\sqrt{y}}^x 2(x-\xi) u(\xi, \psi(x, y, \xi)) d\xi -$$

$$- 2 \int_x^{x+\sqrt{y}} (x-\xi) u(\xi, \psi(x, y, \xi)) d\xi = \int_0^y 2\sqrt{y-\eta} u(x-\sqrt{y-\eta}, \eta) \frac{d\eta}{2\sqrt{y-\eta}} =$$

$$\int_0^y u(x-h, \eta) d\eta - \int_y^0 u(x+h, \eta) d\eta = \int_0^y [u(x-h, \eta) + u(x+h, \eta)] d\eta,$$

ga ega bo'lamiz, bu yerda $h = \sqrt{y-\eta}$.

Shunday qilib, (1) tenglamani quyidagi ko'rinishda yozib olamiz.

$$\int_0^y [u(x-h, \eta) + u(x+h, \eta)] d\eta = f(x, y), \quad (7)$$

Bu yerda $h = \sqrt{y-\eta}$. (7) tenglamaning ikkala qismiga x o'zgaruvchi bo'yicha Furje almashtirishini qo'llaymiz:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{i\lambda x} \int_0^y [u(x+h, \eta) + u(x-h, \eta)] d\eta dx &= \int_0^y \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{i\lambda x} [u(x+h, \eta) + u(x-h, \eta)] dx d\eta = \\ &= \int_0^y [e^{-i\lambda h} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{i\lambda(x+h)} u(x+h, \eta) dx + e^{i\lambda h} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{i\lambda(x-h)} u(x-h, \eta) dx] d\eta = \\ &= \int_0^y [e^{-i\lambda h} \hat{u}(\lambda, \eta) + e^{i\lambda h} \hat{u}(\lambda, \eta)] d\eta = \int_0^y [e^{i\lambda h} + e^{-i\lambda h}] \hat{u}(\lambda, \eta) d\eta = \\ &= 2 \int_0^y \frac{e^{i\lambda h} + e^{-i\lambda h}}{2} \hat{u}(\lambda, \eta) d\eta = 2 \int_0^y \cos \lambda h \hat{u}(\lambda, \eta) d\eta \end{aligned}$$

Demak,
$$\int_0^y \cos \lambda h \hat{u}(\lambda, \eta) d\eta = \hat{f}_1(\lambda, \eta) \quad (8)$$

Bu yerda $f_1 = \frac{1}{2} f$.

(8) tenglamaga y o'zgaruvchi bo'yicha Furje almashtirishini qo'llaymiz:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{i\mu y} \int_0^y \cos \lambda h \hat{u}(\lambda, \eta) d\eta dy = \int_0^{\infty} \hat{u}(\lambda, \eta) \int_{\eta}^{\infty} e^{i\mu y} \cos \lambda \sqrt{y-\eta} dy d\eta$$

Bu tenglikda almashtirish $\tau = y - \eta$, $dy = d\tau$, $y = \tau + \eta$ almashtirish bajarib.

$$\int_0^{\infty} \hat{u}(\lambda, \eta) \int_0^{\infty} e^{i\mu(\tau+\eta)} \cos \lambda \sqrt{\tau} d\tau d\eta = \int_0^{\infty} e^{i\mu\eta} \hat{u}(\lambda, \eta) d\eta \int_0^{\infty} e^{i\mu\tau} \cos \lambda \sqrt{\tau} d\tau = \hat{u}(\lambda, \mu) \int_0^{\infty} e^{i\mu\tau} \cos \lambda \sqrt{\tau} d\tau$$

ni olamiz. Shunday qilib tenglama

$$\hat{u}(\lambda, \mu) I(\lambda, \mu) = \hat{f}_1(\lambda, \mu) \quad (9)$$

ko'rinishni oladi, bu yerda $I = \int_0^{\infty} e^{i\mu\tau} \cos \lambda \sqrt{\tau} d\tau$

$I(\lambda, \mu)$ funksiyani modul quyidan bo'yicha baholashimiz zarur, chunki bu $\hat{u}(\lambda, \mu)$ funksiyalar uchun, so'ngra esa izlanayotgan $u(x, y)$ funksiya uchun baho olishga imkon beradi. U integral λ va μ parametrlarga nisbatan tekis yaqinlashuvchi ekanligini ko'rsatamiz, bunda

μ parametрни umumiylikka zarar yetkazmasdan musbat deb hisoblash mumkin. $t = \sqrt{\tau}$ almashtirishni bajarib va integralda $t^2 = \tau, d\tau = 2tdt$ ekanligini hisobga olib

$I = 2 \int_0^{\infty} e^{i\mu^2 t} t \cos \lambda t dt$ ga ega bo'lamiz. Agar $\tau = t^2$ $\mu < 0$ almashtirishni bajarsak

$$\int_0^{\infty} e^{-i\mu^2 t} t \cos \lambda t dt = \int_0^{\infty} \cos \mu^2 t \cos \lambda t dt - i \int_0^{\infty} \sin \mu^2 t \cos \lambda t dt.$$

$$\int_0^{\infty} e^{i\mu^2 t} t \cos \lambda t dt = \int_0^{\infty} t \cos \mu^2 t \cos \lambda t dt + i \int_0^{\infty} t \sin \mu^2 t \cos \lambda t dt =$$

$$1. \int_0^{\infty} x \cos(ax^2) \cos(2bx) dx = \frac{b}{a} \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2a}} \left[\cos \frac{b^2}{a} C\left(\frac{b}{\sqrt{a}}\right) + \sin \frac{b^2}{a} S\left(\frac{b}{\sqrt{a}}\right) \right]$$

$$2. \int_0^{\infty} x \sin(ax^2) \cos(2bx) dx = \frac{1}{2a} - \frac{b}{a} \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2a}} \left[\sin \frac{b^2}{a} C\left(\frac{b}{\sqrt{a}}\right) - \cos \frac{b^2}{a} S\left(\frac{b}{\sqrt{a}}\right) \right]$$

Bu yerda $x = t, \mu = a, b = \frac{\lambda}{2}$, ([2] Granishteyn kitobidan 478-bet, 2,4-formular)

foydalanib quyidagiga ega bo'lamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{\lambda}{2\mu} \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2\mu}} \left[\cos \frac{\lambda^2}{4\mu} C\left(\frac{\lambda}{2\sqrt{\mu}}\right) + \sin \frac{\lambda^2}{4\mu} S\left(\frac{\lambda}{2\sqrt{\mu}}\right) + \frac{i}{2\mu} - i \frac{\lambda}{2\mu} \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2\mu}} \times \right. \\ &\quad \left. \times \left[\sin \frac{\lambda^2}{4\mu} C\left(\frac{\lambda}{2\sqrt{\mu}}\right) - \cos \frac{\lambda^2}{4\mu} S\left(\frac{\lambda}{2\sqrt{\mu}}\right) \right] \right] = \frac{i}{2\mu} + \frac{\lambda}{2\mu} \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2\mu}} \times \\ &\quad \times \left[\cos \frac{\lambda^2}{4\mu} C\left(\frac{\lambda}{2\sqrt{\mu}}\right) + \sin \frac{\lambda^2}{4\mu} S\left(\frac{\lambda}{2\sqrt{\mu}}\right) - i \sin \frac{\lambda^2}{4\mu} C\left(\frac{\lambda}{2\sqrt{\mu}}\right) + i \cos \frac{\lambda^2}{4\mu} S\left(\frac{\lambda}{2\sqrt{\mu}}\right) \right] = \\ &= \frac{i}{2\mu} + \frac{\lambda}{2\mu} \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2\mu}} \left[C\left(\frac{\lambda}{2\sqrt{\mu}}\right) \left(\cos \frac{\lambda^2}{4\mu} - i \sin \frac{\lambda^2}{4\mu} \right) + i S\left(\frac{\lambda}{2\sqrt{\mu}}\right) \left(\cos \frac{\lambda^2}{4\mu} - i \sin \frac{\lambda^2}{4\mu} \right) \right] = \\ &= \frac{i}{2\mu} + \frac{\lambda}{2\mu} \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2\mu}} \left(\cos \frac{\lambda^2}{4\mu} - i \sin \frac{\lambda^2}{4\mu} \right) \left(C\left(\frac{\lambda}{2\sqrt{\mu}}\right) + i S\left(\frac{\lambda}{2\sqrt{\mu}}\right) \right) = \end{aligned}$$

$\frac{\lambda}{2\sqrt{\mu}} = z$ deb olsak ([2] Granishteyn kitobi 946-bet 8.25-formuladan)

$$C(z) + iS(z) = \sqrt{\frac{i}{2}} \Phi\left(\frac{z}{\sqrt{i}}\right) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_0^z e^{it^2} dt$$

$\cos \frac{\lambda^2}{4\mu} - i \sin \frac{\lambda^2}{4\mu} = e^{-\frac{i\lambda^2}{4\mu}}$ ekanligidan quyidagiga ega bo'lamiz

$$= \frac{i}{2\mu} + \frac{\lambda}{2\mu} \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2\mu}} \frac{2}{2\pi} e^{\frac{i\lambda^2}{4\mu} \frac{\lambda}{2\sqrt{\mu}}} \int_0^{\frac{\lambda}{2\sqrt{\mu}}} e^{it^2} dt = \frac{1}{2\mu} \left(i + \lambda \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2\mu}} \cdot \frac{2}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \cdot e^{\frac{i\lambda^2}{4\mu} \frac{\lambda}{2\sqrt{\mu}}} \int_0^{\frac{\lambda}{2\sqrt{\mu}}} e^{it^2} dt \right)$$

$$I = \frac{1}{\mu} \left(i + \frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{\mu}} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2\mu}} \cdot e^{\frac{i\lambda^2}{4\mu} \frac{\lambda}{2\sqrt{\mu}}} \int_0^{\frac{\lambda}{2\sqrt{\mu}}} e^{it^2} dt \right)$$

$$|I| = \left| \frac{1}{\mu} \left(i + \frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{\mu}} \cdot e^{\frac{i\lambda^2}{4\mu} \frac{\lambda}{2\sqrt{\mu}}} \int_0^{\frac{\lambda}{2\sqrt{\mu}}} e^{it^2} dt \right) \right| \geq \left| \frac{1}{\mu} \right| \left| i + \frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{\mu}} \cdot e^{\frac{i\lambda^2}{4\mu} \frac{\lambda}{2\sqrt{\mu}}} \int_0^{\frac{\lambda}{2\sqrt{\mu}}} e^{it^2} dt \right| = \left| \frac{1}{\mu} \right| \left| 1 - \frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{\mu}} \cdot \int_0^{\frac{\lambda}{2\sqrt{\mu}}} e^{it^2} dt \right|$$

ga ega bo'lamiz. $\left| \int_0^{\frac{\lambda}{2\sqrt{\mu}}} e^{it^2} dt \right| \leq \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2}$ bo'lgani uchun, u holda $|I| = \left| \frac{1}{\mu} \right| \left| 1 - \frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{\mu}} \cdot \int_0^{\frac{\lambda}{2\sqrt{\mu}}} e^{it^2} dt \right| > \frac{1}{\mu} \left| 1 - \frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{\mu}} \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} \right|$

(8) integral λ va μ parametrlarga nisbatan tekis yaqinlashuvchiligini ko'rsatamiz, μ

musbat $\left| 1 - \frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{\mu}} \int_0^{\frac{\lambda}{2\sqrt{\mu}}} e^{it^2} dt \right| > \frac{1}{2}$

$$\frac{\lambda}{2\sqrt{\mu}} = \sqrt{x}$$

uchun $\left| 1 - \frac{\lambda\sqrt{\pi}}{2\sqrt{\mu}} \right| > \frac{1}{2} \quad 1 - \sqrt{\pi}x > \frac{1}{2}; \quad 1 - \sqrt{\pi}x < -\frac{1}{2}$

$$\frac{1}{2} > \sqrt{\pi}x; \quad x < \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\pi}}; \quad x > \frac{3}{2\sqrt{\pi}}$$

$$\frac{\lambda}{2\sqrt{\mu}} \in (-\infty, \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\pi}}) \cup (\frac{3}{2\sqrt{\pi}}, +\infty)$$

ekanligi oson tekshiriladi va boshqa $\frac{\lambda}{2\sqrt{\mu}}$ lar uchun Frenel integrali jadvalidan foydalanib

olish mumkin, chunki

$$|I| = \left| 2 \int_0^{\infty} e^{i\mu^2 t} t \cos \lambda t dt \right| = \left| \int_0^{\infty} e^{i\mu\tau} \cos \lambda \sqrt{\tau} d\tau \right| > \frac{1}{\mu} \tag{10}$$

Buni va (8) formulani hisobga olib

$$|\widehat{u}(\lambda, \mu)| \leq |\widehat{f}(\lambda, \mu)| \tag{11}$$

(11) ni ikkala tarafiga $(1 + \mu^4)$ ni ko'paytirib bo'lamiz.

$$\widehat{u}(\lambda, \mu) = \widehat{f}_1(\lambda, \mu)(1 + \mu^4) \frac{1}{(1 + \mu^4)I(\lambda, \mu)}. \tag{12}$$

$u(x, y)$ ga qo'yilgan shartlardan va (6) dan $\widehat{f}(\lambda, \mu)$ funksiya, L_2 da μ argument bo'yicha tegishlilikini hosil qilamiz.

(10) va (11) dan kelib chiqadiki $(1 + \mu^4)^{-1}(I(\lambda, \mu))^{-1}$ funksiya y o'zgaruvchi bo'yicha (12) formulada aniqlangandek $I_1(\lambda, y)$ funksiyaning Furye obrazidir.

(12) tenglikda Furye usulining teskari almashtirishini μ o'zgaruvchi bo'yicha qo'llaymiz. Teskarilanish teoremasi va Furye almashtirishi differensiallash qoidalaridan foydalanib quyidagilarga ega bo'lamiz:

$$\widehat{u}(\lambda, y) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} I_1(\lambda, y - \eta) \left(E + \frac{\partial^4}{\partial \eta^4} \right) \widehat{f}(\lambda, \eta) d\xi d\eta \quad (13)$$

bu yerda
$$I_1(\lambda, \mu) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-i\mu y} \frac{d\mu}{(1 + \mu^4)I(\lambda, \mu)}$$

$u(x, y)$ funksiya qo'yilgan chegaralar va (6) dan $\widehat{f}(\lambda, y)$ funksiya L_2 da λ argument bo'yicha tegishli ekanligi kelib chiqadi. Hosil bo'lgan tenglamaga λ o'zgaruvchi bo'yicha teskari Furye almashtirishini qo'llaymiz. Teskarilanish teoremasi va svertkalar haqidagi teoremlar va Furye almashtirishini qo'llab 1- masalaning yechimini quyidagi ko'rinishida hosil qilamiz.

$$u(x, y) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} I_2(x - \xi, y - \eta) \left(E + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \xi^2} \right) \left(E + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \eta^2} \right) f(\xi, \eta) d\xi d\eta$$

bu yerda
$$I_2(x - \xi, y - \eta) = -\frac{1}{2} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-i\lambda x} \frac{I_1(\lambda, y)}{1 + \lambda^4} d\lambda.$$
 (6) formula y o'zgaruvchi bo'yicha

lokal xarakterga ega $Supp u \subset D$ shartni inobatga olgan holda (1) tenglamani yechimi uchun (6) ko'rinish $l < \infty$ bo'lganda ham o'rinli ekanligi aniq. U holda (9), (10) va (6) dan (1) boshlang'ich masalaning $C_0^2(\Omega)$ funksiyalar sinfidagi yechimning yagonaligi kelib chiqadi.

(9) tenglamadan (10) ni inobatga olgan holda quyidagi tengsizlikni hosil qilish qiyin emas.

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |\widehat{u}|^2 d\lambda d\mu \leq \frac{1}{2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (1 + |\mu|)^4 |\widehat{f}|^2 d\lambda d\mu. \quad (14)$$

Furye almashtirishni differensiallash xossaligidan foydalanib norma uchun uchburchak tengsizligidan shuningdek (6) va (14) dan: $\|u\|_{L_2} \leq C \|f\|_{W_2^2(R_+^2)}$ ga ega bo'lamiz. Bunda C – o'zgarmas son.

1-teorema isbotlandi.

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